

Correlation between the Cranial Base, Mandible, and Hyoid Bone in Class II Skeletal Individuals- A Cephalometric StudyAbhishek Sinha¹, Sandeep Kaur², Kirandeep Kaur³¹Assistant Professor & Head (Incharge), Department of Dentistry, Patna Medical College, Patna, Bihar, India²Lecturer, Department of Oral Medicine & Radiology, Indira Gandhi Government Dental College & Hospital, Jammu, India³Associate Professor, Department of Periodontology & Implantology, Acharya Shri Chand College of Medical Science & Hospital (ASCOMS) , Jammu, India

Received: 15-06-2024 / Revised: 23-06-2024 / Accepted: 25-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Kirandeep Kaur

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** This study sought to determine how the cranial base, mandible, and hyoid bone relate to one another in the individuals of class II.**Materials and Methods:** Lateral cephalograms from 40 individuals with Skeletal Class II malocclusion were used in a retrospective analysis. Twenty of these subjects had maxillary prognathism, whereas the other twenty had mandibular retrognathism. By examining angle measures using 10 distinct criteria, the study sought to evaluate the link among the base of cranial, mandible, as well as bone (hyoid) in the individuals of class II.**Results:** For both groups, the angles of SARHy, NSHy, C3HyD, and NSAr were measured. There were no discernible variations between the C3HyD and SARHy angles. NSAr and NSHy angles, on the other hand, demonstrated that the groups with maxillary prognathism and mandibular retrognathism differed statistically significantly (p-value < 0.05).**Conclusion:** People with maxillary prognathism had an anteriorly positioned condyle in Skeletal Class II, in contrast to those with mandibular retrognathism. Furthermore, the groups' hyoid bone orientations varied; in maxillary prognathism, it was upward and forward, but in mandibular retrognathism, it was downward and backward.**Keywords:** Cranial base, Mandible Hyoid bone, Skeletal class II Malocclusion.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

In the fields of orthodontics and dentofacial orthopaedics, it is crucial to comprehend the skeletal abnormalities that lead to malocclusion. The treatment and orthodontic mechanics employed are significantly influenced by the clinical diagnosis. Therefore, determining the causes of skeletal discrepancies is essential.

Björk used cephalometric radiographs to establish a link between the jaw base and the cranial base's morphology. [1] The boundaries of the skull and facial skeleton are established by the cranial basis. The nasomaxillary complex is attached to the anterior cranial base, while the mandible is attached to the posterior cranial base. As a result, the maxilla's position is significantly influenced by the form and structure of the anterior cranial base. [2] Alterations in the posterior cranial base also play a crucial role in influencing mandibular positioning. The glenoid fossa, which serves as the point of articulation for the mandible, is directly linked to the posterior cranial base. Changes in the growth or

morphology of this region can affect the positioning of the mandible and contribute to various types of malocclusion. There is a strong connection between sagittal misalignment of the jaws, such as Class II or Class III malocclusions, and alterations in the cranial base. This misalignment is often influenced by the sutural growth of the cranial base, which impacts the relative positioning of both the maxilla and mandible. The synchondroses, key growth sites within the cranial base, play a pivotal role in determining the spatial relationship between the upper and lower jaw, thereby affecting the overall skeletal harmony of the face. [2]

The hyoid bone's ligamentous and muscular attachments, which serve as a useful bridge connecting the skull, cervical spine, and jaw, may be to blame for this. Therefore, any modifications to the hyoid bone's location may have important functional ramifications. The results of earlier research show a strong correlation between

malocclusion and the hyoid bone's position. Jarvinen's study found a connection between face patterns and the SNA and NSAr angles. He found that while smaller NSAr angles correlated with bigger SNA angles, greater NSAr angles were associated with smaller SNA angles. He also showed in 1984 that Class III malocclusions had larger NSAr angular values than Class II malocclusions, with the NSAr angle differing significantly between the two classes. [3,4,5]

It has been shown by researchers that the hyoid bone's location reacts to changes in the anteroposterior position of the head, and that changes in the mandibular position are associated with changes in the hyoid bone. [8].

This study sought to determine how the cranial base, mandible, and hyoid bone relate to each other in people with Class II skeletal patterns, notably those with mandibular retrognathism and maxillary prognathism.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: A study using cephalometry in retrospect

Study Duration: From may 2022 to may 2024

Study Setting: This retrospective study analyzed lateral cephalograms from 40 individuals with skeletal class II malocclusion, using Burstone's NLA and NLB values as reference points. The participants were divided into two groups: 20 with maxillary prognathism and 20 with mandibular retrognathism. All participants were selected from patients who sought orthodontic treatment between 2022 and 2024 at the Department of Orthodontics. Data was collected from patient records at the Dr. A.K. Sinha Memorial Kanchan Dental Clinic, Sona Dental Clinic, and the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopaedics at Patna Medical College and Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria: The study comprised the lateral cephalogram records of people aged 15 to 30 who had a healthy periodontium and a complete set of teeth up to the second molars in both arches.

Exclusion Criteria: The study excluded participants who had undergone orthodontic or surgical treatment in the past, had a history of trauma, diseases, or facial asymmetries, or engaged in practices such as mouth breathing or tongue thrusting.

Procedure

The cephalometric landmarks listed below were employed: [Figure 1]

1. Nasion (N): The frontonasal suture's deepest point.

2. Sella (S): The pituitary fossa's (Sella turcica) midpoint shadow.
 3. Articulare (Ar): The point where the basilar border of the occipital bone and the posterior margin of the mandible meet.
 4. Point D: The mandibular symphysis is located at this point on a lateral cephalogram.
 5. Hyoidale (Hy): The hyoid bone's most anterior and superior tip. 9.
 6. C3: The third cervical vertebra's point at the most inferior anterior position. 9.
- The study's angular measurements.

Saddle angle (NSAr): This angle is formed by the lines that connect Nasion to Sella and Sella to Articulare. It stands for the basal flexure of the skull. [Figure 2]

Hyoidale angle (C3HyD): An angle is formed by a line that runs from C3 to Hyoidale and from Hyoidale to Point D. The superior angle created by the two planes might be interpreted as the hyoidale angle. [Fig. 3]

SArHy angle: This angle is made up of lines that connect Sella and Articulare as well as Articulare and Hyoidale. [Fig. 4]

NSHy angle: This angle is formed by a line connecting Nasion to Sella and Sella to Hyoidale. [Figure 5]

Twenty lateral head films were chosen for a pilot test in which cephalometric tracing was carried out in order to accomplish calibration. To ensure intra-operator dependability, the operator remeasured the same radiographs after two weeks to confirm coincidence and error-free results. The professor traced the identical radiographs two weeks later to be sure there were no mistakes.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 25.0, was used to conduct statistical analyses. NY:

Results

The NSAr, C3HyD, SArHy, and NSHy angles were analyzed in skeletal class II to compare maxillary prognathism with mandibular retrognathism.

1. Saddle Angle (NSAr)

In the maxillary prognathism group, the average saddle angle measured $120.78^{\circ} \pm 5.33$, while the mandibular retrognathic group had a mean of $124.75^{\circ} \pm 4.80$. A statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) was observed between these two groups in the skeletal class II pattern. (See Graph 1 and Table 1).

2. Hyoidale angle (C3HyD)

The mandibular retrognathic group had a mean hyoidale angle of $166.25^{\circ} \pm 17.24$, while the

maxillary prognathism group had a mean of $159.14^\circ \pm 11.87$. The skeleton class II pattern showed a statistically non-significant difference

between the two groups ($p > 0.05$). (Table 1) (Graph 1).

Figure. 1

Figure 2:

Figure 3:

Figure :4:

Figure 5:

Graph 1

Table 1: Comparison of mandibular retrognathism and maxillary prognathism in skeletal class II with respect to NSAr, C3HyD, SarHy, and NSHy angles

skeletal class II	Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	P value
NSAr	Maxillary prognathism	20	120.78	5.33	0.018
	Mandibular retrognathism	20	124.75	4.8	
C3Hy-PtD	Maxillary prognathism	20	159.14	11.87	0.137
	Mandibular retrognathism	20	166.25	17.24	
SArHy	Maxillary prognathism	20	133.33	5.52	0.546
	Mandibular retrognathism	20	134.45	6.13	
NSHy	Maxillary prognathism	20	87.55	3.68	0.001
	Mandibular retrognathism	20	92.95	3.36	

3. SArHyangle

In the maxillary prognathism group, the mean SArHy angle was 133.33° ± 5.52, while in the mandibular retrognathic group, it was 134.45° ± 6.13. The skeleton class II pattern showed a statistically non-significant difference between the two groups (p > 0.05). (Graph 1) (Table 1)

3.4. NSHy angle

The mean NSHy angle was 87.55° ± 3.68 in the maxillary prognathism group, compared to 92.95° ± 3.36 in the mandibular retrognathic group. A significant difference (p < 0.05) was found between the two groups in the skeletal class II pattern (Refer to Table 1 and Figure 1).

Discussion

Orthodontics primarily focuses on understanding development and the features that effect it. One key element is the basicranium, which is lengthened by the speno-occipital synchondrosis and plays a crucial role in postnatal growth. According to Enlow 10, the basal region of the cranium, directly affected by brain development, influences

maxillary growth. However, although the mandible’s growth occurs independently, it is also affected by the position of the glenoid fossa.

Hopkin et al. [11] suggested that abnormalities in sagittal orthodontics could be significantly influenced by the basicranium. Scott 12 further proposed that facial prognathism is impacted by the surface deposition among Nasion as well as Menton.

The anterior cranial base is frequently evaluated using the N-S length. Nonetheless, there has been disagreement about whether the Basion or Articulare should be used to measure the posterior base. For better identification, Bjork 1 suggested using Articulare instead of Basion, and later studies used this method to determine the cranial base’s posterior limit [12].

Over the past 20 years, many research have examined the connection between the hyoid bone, mandible, and skull. Researchers have examined how the hyoid bone adapts to various malocclusions and changes following orthognathic surgery.

In this study, the effects of the cranial base and hyoid bone position on skeletal relationships were analyzed in individuals with a Class II skeletal pattern characterized by maxillary prognathism and mandibular retrognathism. There was a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in the saddle angle (NSAr) in the mandibular retrognathic as well as maxillary prognathic subgroups in Class II, resulting in the mandibular retrognathic group exhibiting higher mean values. statistically noteworthy. This finding is consistent with research by Mestriner, Junior, and Valente 13, which also linked mandibular retrognathism to elevated NSAr values.

The mandibular retrognathic group had greater values of the NSHy angle than the other group, indicating a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$). This implies a potential connection among the NSHy angle and mandibular retrognathism, where the highest mean values were found in subjects with this condition. The hyoid bone's backward and forward movement, in coordination with the mandible, may explain this finding due to muscle attachments between the hyoid bone and the jaw [14].

This study employed the Articulare as a cephalometric landmark, although some researchers, like Varjanne and Koski [15], have favored the Basion due to its closeness to the base of the skull. But Bhatia and Leighton showed that Articulare and Basion were strongly correlated, suggesting that choosing one over the other would not affect the study's conclusions. For this reason, Articulare was selected in the present study, though future studies might consider using Basion for a more comprehensive analysis.

Jarvinen recommended using the Frankfurt plane rather than the SN plane for studies of this nature, as the latter can be rotated, rendering it unreliable [17]. Further research using the Frankfurt plane as a reference could provide more insight. Furthermore, this study did not take into account linear measures of cranial base as well as growth patterns, which have been demonstrated in investigations by Andria et al. [16] as well as Dhopatkar, Bhatia, and Rock 19 to have a bigger influence on skeletal differences. Therefore, more research is required to examine how cranial base angulations as well as hyoid bone position affect skeletal relationships.

Conclusion

In contrast to Skeletal Class II mandibular retrognathism, The condyle was positioned anteriorly in cases of maxillary prognathism. Skeletal class II persons with maxillary prognathism had the hyoid bone oriented upward and forward, whereas those with mandibular retrognathism had it positioned backward and downward.

References

1. Odont ABD. Cranial base development: A follow-up x-ray study of the individual variation in growth occurring between the ages of 12 and 20 years and its relation to brain case and face development. *Am J Orthod.* 1955; 41(3):198–225. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(55)90005-1.
2. Enlow DH. Amorphogenetic analysis of facial growth. *Am J Orthod.* 1966;52(4):283–99. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(66)90169-2.
3. Graber LW. Hyoid changes following orthopedic treatment of mandibular prognathism. *Angle Orthod.* 1978;48(1):33–8. doi:10.1016/0003-3219(1978)048<0033:HCFOTO>2.0.CO;2.
4. Gobeille DM, Bowman DC. Hyoid and muscle changes following distal repositioning of the tongue. *Am J Orthod.* 1976;70(3):282–9. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(76)90334-1.
5. Cuzzo GS, Bowman DC. Hyoid positioning during deglutition following forced positioning of the tongue. *Am J Orthod.* 1975;68(5):564–70. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(75)90087-1.
6. Järvinen S. Relation of the SNA angle to the saddle angle. *Am J Orthod.* 1980;78(6):670–3. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(80)90206-7.
7. Järvinen S. Saddle angle and maxillary prognathism: a radiological analysis of the association between the NSAr and SNA angles. *Br J Orthod.* 1984;11(4):209–13. doi:10.1179/bjo.11.4.209.
8. Mortazavi S, Asghari-Moghaddam H, Dehghani M. Hyoid bone position in different facial skeletal patterns. *J Clin Exp Dent.* 2018;10(4):346–51. doi:10.4317/jced.54657.
9. Stepovich ML. A cephalometric positional study of the hyoid bone. *Am J Orthod.* 1965; 51(12):882–900. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(65)90202-2.
10. Enlow DH, Hunter WS. The growth of the face in relation to the cranial base. *Rep Congr Eur Orthod.* 1968;44:321–35.
11. Hopkin GB, Houston WJ, James GA. The cranial base as an aetiological factor in malocclusion. *Angle Orthod.* 1968;38(3):250–5. doi:10.1043/0003-3219(1968)038<0250:TCBAA A>2.0.CO;2.
12. Scott JH. The analysis of facial growth: I. The anteroposterior and vertical dimensions. *Am J Orthod.* 1958;44(7):507–12. doi:10.1016/0002-9416(58)90083-6.
13. Júnior WM, and AV. Facial prognathism and its relation to the cranial base in Brazilian children with Class I malocclusion. *Rev Odontol Univ Sao.* 1989;3(2):324–33.
14. Bhullar MK, Gupta N, Mittal S. Comparison of Hyoid Bone Position in Skeletal Class I Subjects with Varying Growth Patterns: A

- Cephalometric Study. Dent J Adv. 2021; 9 (1): 27–30. doi:10.1055/s- 0040-171 8648.
15. Varjanne I, Koski K. Cranial base, sagittal jaw relationship and occlusion. A radiological-
craniometric appraisal. Proc Finn Dent. 1982; 78(4):179–83.
16. Bhatia SN, Leighton BC. A Manual of Facial Growth: A Computer Analysis of Longitudinal Cephalometric Growth Data. USA: Oxford University Press; 1993.